

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzyl Chloride by Chromic Acid

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The kinetics of chromic acid oxidation of benzyl chloride in aqueous acetic acid have been investigated. Benzaldehyde has been identified as the only product and it does not seem to be oxidised to benzoic acid under the experimental conditions used. The reaction is first order with respect to each of substrate, oxidant and H^+ . Effect of manganous and cobaltous ions on the reaction suggests a two electron transfer from the substrate to the oxidant. In consonance with the observed effect of 2 : 2'-dipyridyl and 1 : 10-orthophenanthroline, coupled with that of Mn(II) and Co(II) ions on the oxidation a reaction sequence has been formulated. The solvent influence substantiates that the reaction is of ion-dipole type. A tentative mechanism involving the formation of an intermediate chromate ester in a fast step, which subsequently collapses concertedly to afford benzaldehyde and Cr(IV) has been suggested.

ALKYL halides have been oxidised by a variety of oxidants to produce aldehydes and carboxylic acids. For example, Etard's oxidation of benzyl chloride with chromyl chloride affords benzaldehyde¹. Permanganate, hexamethylenetetramine, dimethylsulphoxide and trimethylamine oxide are among the other oxidants which have been used to oxidise benzyl chloride². In this paper kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of this compound by chromic acid in aqueous acetic acid, which have not been reported so far are presented.

Experimental

Materials : Benzyl chloride (B. D. H. sample) was purified, after removing the water with anhydrous sodium sulphate by repeated distillation. The oxidant solution was prepared by dissolving CrO_3 in conductivity water and diluting the solution suitably. Acetic acid was purified by the standard procedure. All other chemicals used in this study were pure samples. AnalaR sodium sulphate was used to adjust the ionic strength to a constant value.

Methods : All the reactions were conducted under pseudo first order conditions in 75% AcOH(v/v) at constant μ of 0.21M and at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, unless otherwise specified. Each reaction was initiated by adding the oxidant solution to a solution containing the substrate, sulphuric acid and sodium sulphate in a reaction bottle. The time of half delivery of the oxidant was reckoned as the zero time of the reaction. The reaction was followed by quenching aliquots at definite time intervals in acidified KI solution and titrating the liberated iodine against standardised thiosulphate with starch as indicator.

Product Analysis : Concentrated solutions of substrate and oxidant were mixed with sufficient

amount of sulphuric acid. After a week when the reaction was complete the components of the reaction mixture were separated by ether extraction. Since chromic acid dissolves in ether to some extent the ether layer was repeatedly shaken with water to draw the chromic acid into the aqueous layer. The ethereal solution was carefully evaporated. The residue was a liquid with the characteristic smell of benzaldehyde and boiling at 179° . In another experiment the combined ether layer was shaken with Borsche's reagent. An orange solid was obtained ; it was quantitatively collected and dried (yield = 92%). This product melted sharply at 235° thereby confirming that it was the 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of benzaldehyde. The reported melting point for this derivative is 237° .

The ether and the aqueous layers, on systematic analysis did not show the presence of any other organic compounds like Ph-COOH, Ph-OH, $(Ph-CH_2)_2$, Ph-CH₂OH, etc. Thus the oxidation of benzyl chloride by chromic acid produces only benzaldehyde. Since benzyl alcohol was not detected it is evident that hydrolysis of benzyl chloride does not take place under the experimental conditions used. It has been reported that this hydrolysis occurs only with an alkali³. This was checked by an independent experiment ; benzyl chloride remained unchanged in presence of sulphuric acid even after several days.

Results and Discussion

Active Species : It has been proved by several authors⁴ that under the pH used in this study the active chromium species is the acid chromate ion, $HCrO_4^-$. The visible spectrum of $CrO_3-H_2SO_4$ solution recorded in this study confirms this. A λ_{max} for $HCrO_4^-$ at 352 nm as reported in the literature was observed.

Effect of Oxidant : In each reaction the rate at which Cr(VI) disappears follows first order kinetics. However, the rate constants are not independent of the initial oxidant concentrations. A decrease in the values of k_1 with increasing [Cr(VI)] is noticed (Table 1). Thus chromic acid appears to be more

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF OXIDANT
[S]=0.065M; [H⁺]=0.3M

[CrO ₃]M × 10 ³	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	3.0
k ₁ × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	4.43	4.28	4.09	4.02	3.98

effective oxidant in the dilute than in the concentrated solutions. Such an observation, also reported by other authors⁵ indicates that the active oxidant in this study is HCrO₄⁻. Increasing dilution increases its concentration thereby increasing the rate constant. Therefore the order of oxidation would be strictly one only with respect to HCrO₄⁻ and not with respect to the gross concentration of Cr(VI).

Effect of Substrate (S) : A first order dependence of the rate on [S] is observed (Table 2). The plot of

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE
[CrO₃]=0.002M; [H⁺]=0.3M

[S]M	0.040	0.050	0.055	0.06	0.07
k ₁ × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	2.66	3.23	3.82	4.13	4.43
k ₁ × 10 ³ lit. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	6.64	6.45	6.92	6.88	6.93
[S]					

k_1 versus [S] is linear passing through the origin. However, this does not necessarily rule out the possibility of formation of a transitory oxidant-substrate complex. It rather indicates that the formation constant of such an intermediate complex is very low.

Effect of H⁺ : A plot of log k_1 versus log [H⁺] is linear with unit slope indicating that the order of the reaction with respect to H⁺ is also one (Table 3). The rate of the reaction may then be written as,

$$\text{rate} = k_1 [\text{oxidant}][S][H^+]$$

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF H⁺
[S]=0.07M; [CrO₃]=0.001M

[H ⁺]M	0.4	0.45	0.5	1.0	1.8
k ₁ × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	2.35	2.75	3.39	6.65	10.51
k ₁ × 10 ³ lit. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	5.88	6.10	6.78	6.65	5.84
[H ⁺]					

Effect of Temperature : The reaction was followed at different temperatures and the k_{specific} values are obtained from the expression,

$$k_{\text{specific}} = \frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{[S][H^+]}$$

The energy of activation and other activation parameters were obtained from the slope of log k_{specific} versus $\frac{1}{T}$ plot and were computed as :

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = 14.9 \text{ K cal mole}^{-1}, \Delta S^\ddagger = -27.0 \text{ e.u. and } \Delta G^\ddagger(30^\circ) = 23.1 \text{ K cal mole}^{-1}.$$

Effect of Solvent : The reaction is most facile in 90% AcOH and increasing proportions of water impede the rate (Table 4). This observation is in

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENT

[S]=0.02M; [CrO₃]=0.001M; [H⁺]=0.3M

Solvent% HOAC-H ₂ O(v/v)	50.50	60.40	70.30	80.20	90.10
k ₁ × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	0.88	1.30	1.81	1.96	4.73

accordance with that observed in a number of chromic acid oxidations. The present reaction is likely to be an ion-dipole type and consequently the activated complex would be less polar than the initial reactant species. There would be increased dispersal of charges in the activated complex compared to the reactants. Consequently, the transition state is less likely to be solvated than the reactants. The observed trend of solvent effect is thus explainable in the light of these assumptions.

Several authors have assumed the formation of acetylchromic acid, CH₃COO—CrO₂OH and its conjugate acid, CH₃COO—CrO₂OH₂⁺ in media containing higher proportions of acetic acid⁶. These acetyl derivatives have been proved to be stronger oxidants than the parent oxidant and this may also be responsible for the enhancement of k_1 with increased acetic acid content of the medium.

The preferential solvation of the reactants also suggests that the rate should be related to the mole fraction of water in the solvent. A plot of log (rate constant) versus mole fraction of water is linear, thereby confirming that the reaction is an ion-dipole type.

Effect of Complexing Agents : Frequently in chromic acid oxidations the interference of complexing agents in the reaction is used to gain an insight on the mode of electron transfers. In this study the effect of 2 : 2'-dipyridyl and 1 : 10-phenanthroline was used for such an investigation; both enhance the rate (Table 5). The argument advanced by earlier investigators to account for a similar observation may well be invoked in the present context⁷. If the formation constant of the intermediate valence state of Cr is more favourable compared to the aquo or aceto complex, the presence of such an intermediate can be inferred from a noticeable change in the reaction rate on adding the complexing agents. In consonance with this

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF COMPLEXING AGENTS

 $[S]=0.02M$; $[CrO_3]=0.001M$; $[H^+]=0.3M$;

Solvent : 80% AcOH(v/v).

$[2:2'$ -dipyridyl] $M \times 10^3$	nil	2	4	6	10
$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	1.96	3.71	5.32	7.13	8.82
$[1:10$ -orthophenanthroline] $M \times 10^3$	nil	2	4	6	10
$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	1.96	3.18	3.89	4.27	4.95

argument bipyridyl and orthophenanthroline may be assumed to increase the lifetime of Cr(IV)—which is formed when the substrate is oxidised by a two electron transfer from Cr(VI)—at the same time favouring the electron transfer. Therefore the valence changes in Cr during reaction may follow the sequence

These two complexing agents may also stabilise Cr(III) species thereby favouring the reaction. However, what exactly is the mode of interaction between the ligand and the Cr species enhancing the rate cannot be *a priori* explained based on this investigation.

Effect of Manganous and Cobaltous Ions : Reduction in rate of chromic acid oxidation by manganous ion has long been used as a diagnostic test to prove to electron transfer. As expected manganous ion impedes the reaction (Table 6). Mn(II)

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF Mn(II) AND Co(II) IONS

 $[S]=0.02M$; $[CrO_3]=0.001M$; $[H^+]=0.3M$;

Solvent : 80% HOAc(v/v).

$[Mn(II)]M \times 10^4$	nil	1	3	5	10
$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	1.96	1.16	1.08	1.02	0.82
$[Co(II)]M \times 10^4$	nil	1	3	5	10
$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	1.96	1.32	1.31	1.26	1.01

is believed to catalyse the disproportionation of Cr(IV) and Cr(V) to Cr(III) and chromate, which would reduce the rate of chromic acid loss⁸. The following sequence may be assumed to account for the observation collected in this investigation.

A parallel effect is noticed by the addition of Co(II) ions and it is likely that Co(II) functions in a manner similar to that by Mn(II).

Mechanism : Since benzoic acid has not been formed it is evident that under the experimental conditions used further oxidation of benzaldehyde

to benzoic acid does not occur. This may be rationalised by the application of mass law effect to the reaction system. Since only a small amount of oxidant is used in relation to benzyl chloride even at the end of the reaction aldehyde is small compared to that of unreacted benzyl chloride. Hence the oxidation of the aldehyde in the presence of excess of benzyl chloride is improbable.

Chromic acid is known to interact with Cl^- to form chlorochromate, $ClCrO_3H^6$. The formation of this species may be expected when benzyl chloride furnishes Cl^- and benzyl carbonium ion by ionisation and hence the reaction may be expected to proceed through benzyl carbonium ion. To test this possibility the visible spectrum of a mixture of the substrate and the oxidant was recorded. The spectrum does not indicate the formation of chlorochromate. This precludes a mechanism involving a carbonium ion intermediate.

It may be assumed that initially a nucleophilic attack on benzyl chloride by $HCrO_4^-$ in presence of H^+ leads to an ester intermediate in a rapid step. This involves loss of HCl. This is supported by the fact that such esters of chromic acid have actually been prepared and characterised (Ref. 1, p. 161). The chromate ester is assumed to break down with concerted switch of electrons in a rate controlling step to give the products. Thus the mechanism of oxidation may be represented as in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

This mechanism is supported by the following evidences. The reaction exhibits first order kinetics with respect to each of substrate, oxidant and H^+ , the overall order being three. The mechanism involves a primary interaction between an ion, $HCrO_4^-$ and a dipole, $Ph-CH_2-Cl$. The observed solvent influence is in concurrence with this mechanism. The entropy of activation is a large negative value (-27 e.u.) validating the formation of a bulky transition state which is more restricted in geometry compared to the reactant species. Addition of HCl to the reaction should suppress reaction by shifting the equilibrium to the left. Attempt to follow the reaction in presence of even low $[HCl]$ ($0.01M$) indicated that the reaction was immeasurably slow. In most of the bimolecular esterification reactions⁸ the activation energy invariably has a value between 14 and 17 K cal mole⁻¹, whereas that for the present reaction is 15.5 K cal mole⁻¹, which lends credibility to ester intermediate. It is interesting to note that the chromic acid oxidation of benzyl alcohol has also been assumed to proceed through a similar ester intermediate. In view of this, comparable activation energies are expected for benzyl alcohol and benzyl chloride oxidations. The value for benzyl alcohol oxidation⁹ is 17 K cal mole⁻¹, a close value to that obtained in the present case. The

mechanism involves a two electron transfer from $HCrO_4^-$ to benzyl chloride. That this is true is substantiated by the observed retardation in the rate on the addition of $Mn(II)$ and $Co(II)$ ions.

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